

PREP4BLUE

METHODS AND TOOLS FOR MISSION OCEAN & WATERS

Preparing the Research & Innovation Core for Mission Ocean, Seas & Waters

Deliverable D6.4

A Helpdesk log and analysis of support benefits and learning outcomes

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Executive Summary

This report summarises the key outcomes and lessons learned from Task 6.4 of the PREP4BLUE project, which aimed to build capacity and support stakeholder engagement under the EU Mission Ocean & Waters.

The **PREP4BLUE Stakeholder Engagement Helpdesk** (HD) was developed as an online and expert-driven support structure offering guidance, tools, and personalised advice to Mission-funded projects. Its main purpose was to foster inclusive and effective stakeholder engagement by helping users identify and apply suitable resources and methodologies. In parallel, it promoted collaboration among the helpdesk teams of the four Mission Lighthouses, the Marine Implementation Platform (MIP), and the PREP4BLUE consortium.

The helpdesk structure included a user-friendly online interface with curated resources on stakeholder engagement, citizen participation, Ocean Literacy, and knowledge transfer. Key materials included:

- A **Toolbox for Citizen Engagement**
- The **Mission Ocean & Waters Social Media Toolkit** and **Digital Academy**
- The **WaveLinks database** of engagement-related initiatives
- A shared **Glossary** to harmonise terminology
- Recordings from both **Citizen** and **Stakeholder Engagement Webinar Series**
- A **Question and Answers** section
- A list of **supporting experts**
- A **form** to facilitate interactions

PREP4BLUE distinguished between citizens and other stakeholder groups, recognising that different engagement strategies and resources are required for individuals acting in a personal capacity versus those representing organised interests. The resources provided were tailored accordingly.

Analysis of Support and Learning Outcomes

The final coordination meeting among the helpdesks highlighted the benefits of structured collaboration and identified several key learning outcomes:

- **Coordination across helpdesks** was essential to avoid duplicated efforts and ensure complementary roles. Regular meetings helped align messages and share best practices.
- A common **communication strategy** proved valuable, with PREP4BLUE and MIP compiling shared content while Lighthouse CSAs supported multilingual outreach.
- Joint development of tools, such as the **Mission Glossary**, contributed to coherence and alignment across different helpdesk structures.
- Despite these successes, **user interaction with helpdesks remained limited**, largely due to the early stages of project implementation, the crowded landscape of ocean-related events, and competing priorities among target audiences. This trend was reflected in participation rates for live training sessions, despite post-event interest in recorded materials.

Conclusions and Implications

Task 6.4 made important strides in improving access to knowledge, harmonising engagement tools, and building an expert support network. However, the underuse of helpdesk services points to a need for improved visibility, targeted outreach, and better alignment with stakeholders' timelines and communication habits.

Looking ahead, the experiences and insights gained through this task offer a solid foundation for future actions supporting stakeholder engagement within Mission Ocean & Waters. Sustained coordination and flexible, accessible support structures will be key to enhancing the visibility and impact of engagement-related resources and services.

Acronyms & Abbreviations

Table 1. Table of abbreviations and acronyms used in Prep4Blue and the document

Acronym / Abbreviation	Signification
AA	Atlantic and Arctic
A-AAGORA	Blueprint for Atlantic-Arctic Agora
ASPC	Atlantic Stakeholder Platform Conference
BlueMission BANOS	Baltic & North Sea Lighthouse CSA
BlueMission AA	Mission Atlantic & Arctic Lighthouse CSA
BlueMission MED	Mediterranean Lighthouse CSA
CSA(s)	Coordination and Support Action project(s)
EC	European Commission
ECOP	Early Career Ocean Professionals
EcoDaLLi	Danube River and Black Sea Lighthouse CSA
FAQ	Frequently Asked Questions
GIS	Geographical Information System
HD	Helpdesk
MED	Mediterranean
MIP (Ocean)	Mission Ocean & Waters Implementation Platform
(the) Mission	Mission 'Restore Our Ocean & Waters by 2030' / Mission Ocean & Waters / Mission Ocean and Waters
P4B	PREP4BLUE
R&I	Research and Innovation
Q&A	Questions and Answers

1 Introduction

1.1 Mission Restore Our Ocean and Waters

Missions are a novel instrument in Horizon Europe, with the aim of tackling societal challenges with systemic solutions. The implementation of five thematic missions by 2030 (Restore our Ocean and Waters; Adaptation to Climate Change; Cancer; Climate-Neutral and Smart Cities; Soil Health and Food) was launched in 2021 by a [Commission Communication on European Missions](#). The objective of the Mission 'Restore our Ocean and Waters by 2030' is to provide a systemic approach for the restoration of our ocean, seas and waters by 2030.

The Mission Restore our Ocean and Waters (hereafter 'the Mission' or 'Mission Ocean and Waters') is implemented in two phases: a first "development and piloting" phase (2021-2025), followed by a second "deployment and upscaling" phase (2026-2030). During the first phase, the Mission rolled out four "Lighthouses", which are Coordination and Support Action projects (CSAs) to support the research and innovation projects in major European sea and river basins: the Atlantic & Arctic Sea basin ([BlueMissionAA](#)¹), Baltic & North Sea ([BlueMissionBANOS](#)²), Danube river and Black Sea ([EcoDaLLI](#)³) and Mediterranean Sea ([BlueMissionMed](#)⁴) [1]. Moreover, the Mission Ocean & Waters Implementation Platform (MIP Ocean) supports the European Commission's implementation by facilitating knowledge-sharing, communication and technical assistance across the Mission community, linking the Mission Secretariat with technical assistants from CSAs and PREP4BLUE. Figure 1 shows the Mission Ocean & Waters Ecosystem, indicating the connections established between PREP4BLUE, the Mission Implementation Platform (MIP), and Basins' CSAs.

Figure 1. Mission Ocean & Waters Ecosystem. Source: PREP4BLUE project

¹ <https://bluemissionaa.eu/>

² <https://bluemissionbanos.eu/>

³ <https://ecodalli.eu/>

⁴ <https://bluemissionmed.eu/>

1.2 Purpose of this report

This report presents the results of Task 6.4 of the PREP4BLUE project, which aimed to build capacity and support stakeholder engagement within the Mission Ocean & Waters.

The purpose of this report is twofold:

1. **To describe the functioning and outcomes of the stakeholder engagement help desk** established under this task. The help desk was designed to provide on-demand support to all Mission funded projects, offering guidance, tools, and expert advice to overcome challenges and promote inclusive and effective engagement processes. It also fostered exchange and collaboration among teams involved in the Help Desk (HD) development related to the Mission, particularly those of the four Lighthouses CSAs and the MIP.
2. **To analyse the added value and learning outcomes** derived from both the help desk support and the **capacity-building activities** developed to support organisations and individuals involved in stakeholder engagement for the Mission Ocean and Waters. These activities included a series of virtual training sessions and resource materials designed to help upskill facilitators and champions in the practical application of methods and tools outlined in the [Stakeholder Engagement Guidelines](#) (D6.1).

Overall, the report contributes to the overarching objective of PREP4BLUE to strengthen stakeholder involvement, co-creation, and participatory governance within the Mission Ocean and Waters. The findings presented are intended to inform future actions by Mission-related initiatives.

2 Helpdesk structure and interactions

The Helpdesk was designed to assist any stakeholder involved in the Mission Ocean and Waters Lighthouses in identifying and utilizing resources that Prep4Blue has catalogued and generated. These resources aim to facilitate processes such as stakeholder engagement, citizen participation, Ocean Literacy, and Knowledge Transfer to support the achievement of the Mission's objectives. The site also includes answers to FAQs and a contact form. In addition to the online information, the HD provided the expertise of a prominent network of specialists to advise and address specific queries regarding the catalogued tools.

Figure 2. PREP4BLUE Helpdesk structure, detailing the resources developed within the HD activity

2.1 Resources

Public mobilisation, citizen and stakeholder engagement are crucial elements of Mission Ocean and Waters. Within the PREP4BLUE project, both citizen and stakeholder engagement were addressed. The direct engagement of individual citizens acting on their behalf requires a different approach than the involvement of more organised stakeholder groups sharing a common interest or objective. For this reason, P4B developed specific deliverables and activities to support the citizen engagement in one hand, and addressing stakeholders' mobilisation in the other.

This section of the HD provides a rapid access to a selection of the most relevant resources developed by PREP4BLUE to support these processes. It also provides a link to the section including all project results.

Resources directly linked are:

- **Toolbox for citizen engagement** containing approaches, case studies and practical advice for driving citizen engagement with your Mission project actions.
- **Mission Ocean & Waters Social Media Toolkit**, providing materials and support in support to social media communication.
- **Mission Ocean & Waters Digital Academy** to upskill project teams on best social media practices and digital skills.
- **WaveLinks**, an innovative and interactive database to identify projects, citizen science initiatives, stakeholders, engagement methods, events, services, policies and funding opportunities.
- **Glossary**, offering short, detailed explanations for common terms used in the framework of the project. This resource, developed in collaboration by the P4H HD teams of P4B, the Mission's CSAs and the MIP is further described in section 2.1.1
- **Citizen Engagement Webinar Series** recordings, further described in section 2.1.2.
- **Stakeholder Engagement Webinar Series** recordings, further described in section 2.1.2.

The following subsection describes the resources developed by the P4B HD team, not reported in previous project deliverables.

2.1.1 PREP4BLUE Glossary

This resource aims to facilitate clearer communication and alignment among key actors involved in the Mission's implementation, including the PREP4BLUE project team, Lighthouse Coordination and Support Actions (CSAs) projects, the Mission Ocean & Waters Implementation Platform (MIP Ocean), and the European Commission.

The glossary enables greater coherence in the use of language across multidisciplinary activities by providing explanatory entries derived from recognised and credible sources. It functions as a practical reference for stakeholders and partners, supporting effective collaboration throughout the Mission.

As shown in Table 2, the glossary (see Annex 7.1) is presented in a tabular format and includes the following fields. Please note that not all terms contain entries in every field:

- **Topic** – The thematic area relevant to the Mission Ocean and Waters.
- **Term** – The concept or phrase being explained.
- **Acronym** – Commonly used abbreviation, where applicable.
- **Definition** – A clear, sourced explanation of the term.
- **Source** – A link to the source of the definition.
- **Citation** – A bibliographic reference to acknowledge the original source.

Table 2. Example of a glossary entry including all fields

	TOPIC	TERM	ACRONYM	DEFINITION	SOURCE	CITATION
61	Awareness campaigns & Ocean Literacy	Ocean literacy	OL	Understanding of the ocean’s influence on human beings and their influence on the ocean.	http://www.coexploration.org/oceanliteracy/documents/OceanLitChart.pdf	National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration (NOAA) (2013). Ocean Literacy: The Essential Principles and Fundamental Concepts of Ocean Sciences for Learners of All Ages. Version 2.

This compilation of terms builds upon earlier efforts such as the glossary developed in the MATES blueprint project⁵. Originally delivered in January 2024, it has since been progressively expanded integrating contributions from PREP4BLUE, A-AAGORA and MIP.

As illustrated in Figure 3, the glossary currently includes a wide range of terms related to the Mission’s priority areas. These include citizen and stakeholder engagement, ocean literacy, socio-ecological management, social innovation, and other key topics. The glossary is intended as a living document, designed to ease its continuous use in collaboration with Mission actors. By supporting consistent terminology, it contributes to the broader goals of capacity building, knowledge transfer, and effective stakeholder engagement promoted by PREP4BLUE.

Figure 3. Classification of terms at the version 4.0 of the Glossary, issued in April 2025, which counts with 90 terms.

⁵MATES - Maritime Alliance for fostering the European Blue Economy through a Marine Technology Skilling Strategy (Erasmus+ blueprint project 591889-EPP-1-2017-1-ES-EPPKA2-SSA-B; 2018-2022) <https://www.projectmates.eu>

2.1.2 Stakeholder engagement webinar series

In order to build capacity and support stakeholder engagement with the R&I goals of the Mission Ocean and Waters a series of [stakeholder engagement capacity building webinars](#) (Figure 4) were developed.

The activity, initially designed as a series of six webinars in 2024, was extended with a supplementary event in 2025 which created a debate on the PREP4BLUE main outputs. The webinars explored diverse approaches to stakeholder engagement and co-creation in ocean and water-related initiatives. Topics ranged from climate adaptation in aquaculture and marine biodiversity valuation, to blue economy development, water scarcity governance, and citizen engagement in river and marine conservation. Last session was aimed at showcasing best practices of shared governance models for engaging stakeholders and citizens in marine and coastal issues, offering support to Regional Authorities by presenting PREP4BLUE’s findings and exploring opportunities for interregional cooperation. Each session featured practical case studies covering all the four Lighthouse areas, which provided practical insights and actionable strategies to help future projects foster collaboration and innovation. The connections across the Missions ‘Ocean and Waters’ and ‘Climate Change Adaptation’ were explored analysing similitudes in the stakeholder engagement landscape.

Figure 4. Summary of Stakeholder engagement webinars, held between 2024 and 2005. Source: Authors’ elaboration

These webinars were specifically designed to address some of the critical needs identified by the project, such as advancing stakeholder engagement maturity levels and fostering co-creation among diverse actors. The different themes of the sessions were mainly addressing objectives 1⁶ and 3⁷ of the Mission Ocean & Waters, keeping a strong focus on the enabler 2⁸. Stakeholder discussions and recommendations address a central question: *How can Stakeholder engagement improve the Mission Restore our Ocean and Waters implementation?*

⁶ Objective 1: Protect and Restore marine & freshwaters ecosystems & biodiversity

⁷ Objective 3: Carbon neutral & circular Blue Economy

⁸ Enabler 2: Public mobilization & engagement

The first six webinars generated great interest, with more than 400 visits to the registration page. A total of 114 people attended, and during the PREP4BLUE period of activity, the recordings were viewed a total of 262 times, as detailed in Table 3. Only a few satisfaction surveys' responses were received (8), but those respondents indicated they met their expectations and found them very useful (4,75 over 5 in both cases), and the overall evaluation was 4,65 over 5.

Table 3. Indicators of impact of the webinar series, detailing the Lighthouse and Mission objective addressed, as well as the number of attendees and visualisations

Title	Date	LH	Mission Objective addressed	Nº of attendees	Nº of visualizations
Bridging Missions: Stakeholder Engagement Strategies for Climate Change Adaptation and Ocean Initiatives	03/07/2024	AA	3 (sustainable aquaculture)	28	36
From Stakeholders Engagement to Policy: Assessing Marine Biodiversity Value	17/07/2024	AA	1 (biodiversity protection)	38	30
The ups and downs of delivering a sustainable blue economy ecosystem – the Orkney experience	31/07/2024	BANOS	3 (Blue economy)	14	21
Co-creation for Transformational Adaptation to Water Scarcity under Deep Uncertainty	02/10/2024	MED	1 (Restore free flowing rivers)	14	37
Proxecto Rios: connecting rivers and people in Galicia. How coordination, commitment and enthusiasm can create ecological citizenship; From Puzzle to Purpose: Inspiring Community Engagement with the Danube through Co-Creation and Storytelling	16/10/2024	Danube	1 (Restore free flowing rivers)	9	23
Engaging Stakeholders for Effective Advocacy and Governance of Highly Protected MPAs in the Mediterranean Sea	30/10/2024	MED	1 (Marine Protected Areas)	11	115
TOTAL				114	262

2.2 Frequently Asked Questions

PREP4BLUE developed a series of 11 Questions & Answers (Q&A) to inform on PREP4BLUE project and the Mission Ocean & Waters. These were complemented by 21 additional Q&As contributed by Blue Mission BANOS, based on the PREP4BLUE Tool for Citizen Engagement. A compilation of all Q&As is accessible through the Help Desk website⁹.

Figure 5. Image of the FAQ section, displaying the 11 questions and answers developed by PREP4BLUE presenting the project and the Mission, along with a button linking to the full compilation of Q&As, including those contributed by BlueMissionBANOS.

2.3 Panel of experts

In order to assemble as much expertise as possible to answer the questions that could be posed to the HD team, a Panel of Experts was organised. Participants in the high-level events related to the Mission Ocean and Waters, held in October 2023, interviewed as part of P4B T6.5¹⁰, were invited to take part in this panel. This way, the HD could ensure a wider expertise in the different European Sea Basins and include the views from early-researchers & students to experienced professionals.

15 external experts and stakeholders out of 37 accepted to provide their support to PREP4BLUE implementation through any of the following means:

- Facilitating access to information of relevance to the project activities: reports, additional experts, background projects, key technologies, *etc.*
- Expanding the project network to ensure PREP4BLUE covers all relevant aspects identified in the Project Description, major geographic areas in Europe (sea-basins) and all type of agents (industry, education and academia, administration, society at large).
- Responding to consultation processes launched within the project.

The anticipated time commitment for their involvement was expected to average a maximum of 1 to 3 full-time working days throughout the project's duration.

⁹ https://prep4blue.eu/wp-content/uploads/2024/05/P4B_QA_v2.pdf

¹⁰ In October 2023, the PREP4BLUE team undertook 56 interviews at a series of high-level events related to the Mission Ocean held in the vicinity of Galicia (NW of Spain): these include the [EurOcean Conference](#), the [EMB ECOP \(Early Career Ocean Professionals\) Network Forum](#), and the 10th Atlantic Stakeholder Platform Conference ([ASPC 2023](#)). The results of these interviews are detailed in P4B D6.5 Pathways to develop capacity/skills needs to achieve the Mission targets by 2030.

On the other hand, WP leaders were invited to decide *ad hoc* which Experts to consult on each occasion and how best to approach them when their input is needed. Contributions of individual experts will be duly acknowledged through the reports and materials delivered by the project.

A Terms of Reference document was prepared, providing details about the organization of this group. This document ensured transparency and equal relationship of the project with the external experts.

Figure 6. Example of the display of one of the experts' information

The necessary information to showcase expert's profile and main expertise was collected with a registering, and this information was displayed in the P4B HD, as shown in Figure 6.

Figure 7. Characterisation of the panel by Countries

The panel covered nine European countries, as shown in Figure 7. The majority of experts were developing their activity in research centres, universities or laboratories, as shown in Figure 8.

Figure 8. Characterisation of the panel by type of organisation

Despite the group invited to take part in the panel was balanced in terms of gender, women showed a much lower rate of integration in the group. This has resulted in an unbalanced panel in terms of gender with the double of men than women, as shown in Figure 9. The reasons for this different response may be diverse in each case, but considering this result, the HD team would recommend to increase efforts in mobilising women in order to get gender balanced panels.

Figure 9. Characterisation of the invited experts and the resulting panel by gender

2.4 Help-desk interactions

Close to the end of the PREP4BLUE project activity, in April 2025, there have been 713 visits to the Helpdesk. Nevertheless, there was just a single consultation through the consultation form concerning WaveLinks' access.

This lack of user interaction with the helpdesk was consistent with the results that the Lighthouse helpdesk teams were receiving; from the exchanges done with the rest of Mission Ocean and Waters HD teams (detailed in section 3), only the MIP HD was receiving an important number of requests. The differences among those levels of interactions are probably due to the different nature of the MIP helpdesks in relation to the ones of the Lighthouses and PREP4BLUE, but they also may indicate a need for better communication and resource visibility.

3 Coordination with other Mission initiatives

PREP4BLUE helpdesk contributed to the coordination of the Mission HDs by coordinating a series of 14 meetings to support each other in the development of the projects' helpdesks. Those started in October 2023 and finalised in April 2025. Participants included the MIP and the Lighthouses CSAs. Their degree of involvement varied depending on the different degree of dedication of efforts to the HD activities, and also to the dates of launch of the HD activity.

In this way, the MIP HD team, the first starting its activity and the one receiving the most requests, participated actively in most of the meetings, while BlueMissionMed and BlueMissionBANOS, which does not have a HD as such, only participated in a few meetings to align their activity and share information.

Figure 10. Projects coordinated to join efforts on the Help-desk development

The following sections delve into the main themes discussed during these meetings, providing insights into the coordination efforts and collaboration strategies implemented across helpdesk teams.

3.1 Identifying the Mission's helpdesk community

Understanding the structure of the Mission HDs by identifying the different targets of each one of them, and the teams involved in their development. As a result, an excel file with contact information and main activities of the development of the HDs was developed¹¹. The most relevant information about the nature and targets of these HDs are presented in Table 4.

¹¹ Uploaded and shared in the Technopolis Sharefile: https://technopolisLtd223.sharepoint.com/:x/s/4198-Missionoceanseasandwatersimplementationsupportplatform/EWchXzE51R9OitxhZS_OfoQB9Uy497sLV7_fzODpI8jQPQ?rttime=E5cGQtqV3Ug

Table 4. Nature and targets of the Mission Ocean & Waters helpdesks, including those of the MIP, PREP4BLUE and the four lighthouse CSAs.

Nature	Mission 's Project	HD target objectives
Includes resources and tools for interaction	<p>Mission Implementation Platform (MIP)</p>	<p>Assist the Mission secretariat, mainly classifying the Pledges and uploading them to the maritime forum.</p> <p>Maintain the communication with stakeholders contacting the Mission</p> <p>Develop statistical analysis and reporting</p>
	<p>PREP4BLUE</p>	<p>Support Mission's community (MIP & CSAs) in addressing stakeholder and citizen engagement, knowledge management, communication, business models, regulation and financial ecosystems</p>
	<p>BlueMissionAA</p>	<p>Support Mission's projects in the Atlantic and Arctic area on business and innovation</p>
Includes resources or tools, not focusing direct interaction with users	<p>EcoDaLLi</p>	<p>Develop and maintain a catalogue of services in the EcoDaLLi portal, mainly focused on innovation, business and innovation transfer</p>
	<p>BlueMission BANOS</p>	<p>Facilitate the access to most relevant information on citizen engagement translating 21 Q&A translated to Baltic and North Sea languages.</p> <p>Focussed in engaging with the Mission, with a strong focus in citizens</p>
	<p>BlueMissionMed</p>	<p>Promote a platform for stakeholder matchmaking addressed to business</p> <p>Inspire stakeholders by developing a catalogue of solutions for innovative approaches to environmental challenges in the Mediterranean</p>

4 Analysis of support benefices and learning outcomes

The final meeting of the Mission helpdesks community included a collective reflection on the benefits provided and lessons learned throughout their activities.

One of the key insights discussed was the complex structure of the Mission Ocean & Waters initiative, which involved several helpdesks (HDs) being launched at different times and with varying scopes. This diversity highlighted the importance of coordination to avoid duplication of efforts. In this context, regular coordination meetings promoted by PREP4BLUE's HD team proved to be particularly valuable.

One of the solutions found to complement the HD activities was the selection of communication languages to spread a common information. In this sense, MIP and PREP4BLUE focused on the compilation of relevant information from the Mission HDs community, whilst the Lighthouses CSAs dedicated efforts to the translations in their areas' languages.

This collaboration extended to the co-creation of communication tools and resources, such as the glossary. The resulting synergy led to the adoption of similar structural approaches by various helpdesks (*e.g.*, PREP4BLUE and BlueMissionAA), the creation of a glossary comprising 90 terms to support clear Mission-related communication, and the joint use of templates for organising content.

Despite these efforts, participants acknowledged a general lack of user interaction across all the Mission's CSAs helpdesks¹². This underutilization was attributed partly to limited visibility and insufficient promotion of helpdesk resources. Another factor was the project timeline: most stakeholders targeted by these initiatives were in the early stages of launching their Mission-related activities during this period. Additionally, the high volume of ocean-related events contributed to limited stakeholder availability. This challenge was also noted during the stakeholder engagement webinar series, where many interested individuals cited schedule conflicts as a barrier to participation. Although a portion of them accessed the webinar recordings later, some users still reported difficulties in keeping up.

5 Conclusion

In summary, while the PREP4BLUE helpdesk initiative demonstrated clear benefits in terms of coordination, knowledge sharing, and the development of common communication resources, its full potential has yet to be realised due to visibility and timing challenges. Strengthening communication strategies, enhancing the visibility of support services, and aligning engagement efforts with stakeholders' availability will be essential for increasing the future effectiveness and impact of the helpdesks network. These findings underscore the importance of continuous coordination and flexible support mechanisms within the evolving framework of Mission Ocean and Waters.

¹² This includes PREP4BLUE and the four Lighthouses CSAs

6 Bibliography

- [1] D. E. Kampa *et al.*, ‘Baseline Study for the Implementation of Lighthouses of the Mission “Restore our Ocean and Waters by 2030”’, Publications Office of the European Union, Report, Sep. 2022. doi: [10.2777/34856](https://doi.org/10.2777/34856).

7 ANNEXES

7.1 Glossary

Deliverable D6.4

Glossary of Prep4Blue common terms

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This document was created initially to be shared among the Mission Ocean & Water programme' participants (Prep4Blue, LH CSAs, MPI & EC) in order to promote a consistent use of the Mission's terminology.

The table has the following headings:

- **Topic:** Following a list of pre-defined Topics related with the Mission Ocean and Waters objectives.
- **Term:** Name of the term to be defined
- **Acronym:** Capital letters commonly used for the term (if applicable)
- **Definition:** definition provided to the term
- **Source:** Link where the definition can be found
- **Citation:** Reference to indicate the origin of the definition. Please use it to quote the definition.

	TOPIC	TERM	ACRONYM	DEFINITION	SOURCE	CITATION
1	Awareness campaigns & Ocean Literacy	Behaviour change		Any modification in behaviour altering the way in which the individual acts of reacts. The change may happen spontaneously and involuntarily without any intervention, or it may be systematic and prompted by conditioning.	https://psychologydictionary.org/	Psychology Dictionary
2	Socio-ecological management	Behaviour Change Wheel	BCW	It is a systematic way of identifying relevant intervention functions and policy categories based on what is understood about the target behaviour	https://www.behaviourchange-wheel.com/about-wheel	
3	Socio-ecological management	Blue biotechnology		It is the application of science and technology to living aquatic organisms for the production of knowledge, goods and services	https://oceans-and-fisheries.ec.europa.eu/ocean/blue-economy/blue-bioeconomy-and-blue-biotechnology_en	OECD, 2016. Roberts, J. (ed.) (2016), Blue Biotechnology, Commonwealth Blue Economy Series, No. 5, Commonwealth Secretariat, London, https://doi.org/10.14217/9781848599468-en .
4	Socio-ecological management	Blue carbon sequestration		It is a process in which carbon dioxide is removed from the atmosphere and stored in Coastal Blue carbon ecosystems (BCE): mangroves, seagrass meadows and tidal marshes	https://oceanpanel.org/wp-content/uploads/2023/06/Ocean_Panel_Blue_Carbon_Handbook-1.pdf	Schindler Murray, L., Milligan, B. et al. 2023. "The blue carbon handbook: Blue carbon as a nature based solution for climate action and sustainable development." Report. London: High Level Panel for a Sustainable Ocean Economy.
5	Awareness campaigns & Ocean Literacy	Blue forest		It is a term often used to describe underwater ecosystems	https://www.unep.org/news-and-stories/story/blue-forests-finding-coastal-and-marine-solutions-meet-paris-agreement	
6	Awareness campaigns & Ocean Literacy	Blue schools		Schools committed to empower educators, students and educational communities to help integrate and promote Ocean Literacy principles.	http://www.seachangeproject.eu/images/SEACHANGE/Media_Centre/sc_KA_booklet.pdf	-
7	Fisheries/Aquaculture	Bottom trawling		It is a fishing practice that herds and captures the target species, like ground fish or crabs, by towing a net along the ocean floor	https://www.fisheries.noaa.gov/national/bycatch/fishing-gear-bottom-trawls	-
8	Citizen & Stakeholder engagement	Brainstorming		A method for generating a range of creative solutions to a problem by having participants come up with as many ideas as possible.	https://www.fws.gov/stakeholder-engagement/techniques	

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9	Fisheries/Aquaculture	Bycatch		Discarded catch of marine species and unobserved mortality due to a direct encounter with fishing vessels and gear	https://www.fisheries.nooa.gov/insight/understanding-bycatch	-
10	Socio-ecological management	Carbon-neutral economy		It refers to having a balance between emitting carbon and absorbing carbon from the atmosphere in carbon sinks. So, the aim is to offset emissions made in one sector by reducing them somewhere else. This can be done through investment in renewable energy, energy efficiency or other clean, low-carbon technologies. The EU's emissions trading system (ETS) is an example of a carbon offsetting system.	https://www.europarl.europa.eu/news/en/headlines/society/20190926STO62270/what-is-carbon-neutrality-and-how-can-it-be-achieved-by-2050?&at_campaign=20234-Green&at_medium=Google_Ads&at_platform=Search&at_creation=RSA&at_goal=TR_G&at_audience=carbon%20neutral&at_topic=Carbon_Neutral&at_location=ES&gclid=EAlaIqobChMIh-Hgi6ulgMV6hQGAB3pDglxEAMYASAAEgIRIPD_BwE	
11	Citizen & Stakeholder engagement	Charette		A collaborative meeting where project stakeholders attempt to resolve conflicts and draft solutions to a design/planning problem in a limited period of time.	https://www.fws.gov/stakeholder-engagement/techniques	Charette
12	Socio-ecological management	Circular economy		It is a system which maintains the value of products, materials and resources in the economy for as long as possible, and minimises the generation of waste. This means a system where products are reused, repaired, remanufactured or recycled	https://eur-lex.europa.eu/EN/legal-content/glossary/circular-economy.html	-
13	Citizen & Stakeholder engagement	Citizen		Any member of a society in which PREP4BLUE is active. In general, when used in PREP4BLUE, 'citizens' emphasizes the non-specialist and non-elite nature of the individuals in question	https://www.oecd-ilibrary.org/governance/innovative-citizen-participation-and-new-democratic-institutions_b40aab2a-en	Chwalisz, C. (2020), "Good practice principles for deliberative processes for public decision making", in Innovative Citizen Participation and New Democratic Institutions: Catching the Deliberative Wave, OECD Publishing, Paris,
14	Citizen & Stakeholder engagement	Citizen advisory board		A group of stakeholders, often representing a particular community, convened to provide comments on a particular issue or project.	https://www.fws.gov/stakeholder-engagement/techniques	

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15	Citizen & Stakeholder engagement	Citizen Assembly		An organised coming together of citizens for a particular purpose that engages with Mission Ocean. Citizen assemblies should ensure diversity of participants; allow space for deliberation , and lead to participants making informed decisions/recommendations	https://www.fide.eu/	
16	Citizen & Stakeholder engagement	Citizen Science/Participatory Science	CS/PS	Citizen Science promotes the collaboration between non-professionals and scientists and in a two-way process. Citizens can engage in various degrees from co-design and co-creation, through problem definition, data collection, analysis, and dissemination of results, to participation as interpreters of information and sensors...The benefits are shared: scientists enhance their monitoring and analytical capacities and citizens gain scientific knowledge, awareness, and recognition. Citizen science is often described as “public participation in scientific research.”	-	Garcia-Soto et al (2021). Marine Citizen Science: Current State in Europe and New Technological Developments, <i>Frontiers in Marine Science</i> 8: 1-13
17	Citizen engagement	Civil Society Organizations	CSO	A civil society organisation is an organisational structure whose members serve the general interest through a democratic process and which plays the role of mediator between public authorities and citizens. Examples of such organisations include: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - social partners (trades unions and employers’ groups); - non-governmental organisations (e.g. for environmental and consumer protection); - grassroots organisations (e.g. youth and family groupings). 	https://eur-lex.europa.eu/EN/legal-content/glossary/civil-society-organisation.html	
18	Citizen & Stakeholder engagement	co-assessment		focuses on involving citizens and stakeholders in the identification of what can be considered a successful outcome	https://op.europa.eu/en/publication-detail/-/publication/6f3a03af-f2fb-11ee-8e14-01aa75ed71a1/language-en	
19	Citizen & Stakeholder engagement	co-creation		refers to activities aimed at the collaborative production of tangible outcomes, which are typically initiated by on the actors of the quadruple-helix but including contribution from all helixes.	https://op.europa.eu/en/publication-detail/-/publication/6f3a03af-f2fb-11ee-8e14-01aa75ed71a1/language-en	
20	Citizen & Stakeholder engagement	co-design		refers to activities aimed at consulting citizens about R&I related topics with a view to identifying needs, ideas, priorities, and recommendations	https://op.europa.eu/en/publication-detail/-/publication/6f3a03af-f2fb-11ee-8e14-01aa75ed71a1/language-en	

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21	Citizen & Stakeholder engagement	Collaborate		To partner with the public in each aspect of the decision including the development of alternatives and the identification of the preferred solution	https://iap2canada.ca/Resources/Documents/07-02-Foundations-Spectrum-MW-rev2%20(1).pdf	
22	Citizen & Stakeholder engagement	Community of Practice	CoP	"[A community] of practice [is a group] of people who share a concern, a set of problems, or a passion about a topic, and who deepen their knowledge and expertise in this area by interacting on an ongoing basis"	-	1) Wenger, E., McDermott, R.A., Snyder, W., (2002). <i>Cultivating Communities of Practice: A Guide to Managing Knowledge</i> . Harvard Business School Press, Boston, Massachusetts. 2) Vetter, T. 2020. Social (un-)learning and the legitimization of marginalized knowledge: How a new community of practice tries to 'kick the grain habit' in ruminant livestock farming, <i>Journal of Rural Studies</i> 79: 11-23
23	Awareness campaigns & Ocean Literacy	Competence		The proven ability to use knowledge, skills and personal, social and/or methodological abilities, in work or study situations, and in professional and personal development.	https://ec.europa.eu/ploteus/sites/eac-efq/files/en.pdf	Council Recommendation of 22 May 2017 on the European Qualifications Framework for lifelong learning and repealing the Recommendation of the European Parliament and of the Council of 23 of April of 2008 on the establishment of the European Qualifications Framework for lifelong learning. European Commission ESCO Handbook, European Skills, Competences, Qualifications and Occupations, © European Union, 2017
24	Citizen & Stakeholder engagement	Consult		To obtain public feedback on analysis, alternatives and/or decisions	https://iap2canada.ca/Resources/Documents/07-02-Foundations-Spectrum-MW-rev2%20(1).pdf	

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25	Awareness campaigns & Ocean Literacy	Cross-sector knowledge, skills and competences		Refers to knowledge, skills and competences that are relevant to occupations across several economic sectors	https://ec.europa.eu/ploteus/sites/eac-eqf/files/en.pdf	European Commission ESCO Handbook, European Skills, Competences, Qualifications and Occupations, © European Union, 2017
26	Social innovation	Data Integration and Extension for Grant Ontology	DINGO	is an ontology expressly designed to provide an extensible interoperable framework for formally conceptualizing and expressing the relevant parts of the research/cultural landscape in relation to funding, such that they can easily be shared between different actors and platforms.	https://zenodo.org/records/10944474	
27	Citizen & Stakeholder engagement	Delphi method		An iterative survey method used to uncover the range of opinions or build agreement among a group of experts without the need for face-face meetings.	https://www.fws.gov/stakeholder-engagement/techniques	
28	Digital twins	Digital Twin of the Ocean	DTO	A digital twin is a digital representation of real-world entities or processes. Digital twins use real-time and historical data to represent the past and present and numerical models to simulate future scenarios. Digital twins bridge the gap between the physical and digital domains, enabling better decision-making and problem-solving.	A-AAGORA project glossary. https://research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/funding/funding-opportunities/funding-programmes-and-open-calls/horizon-europe/eu-missions-horizon-europe/restore-our-ocean-and-waters/european-digital-twin-ocean-european-dto_en	
29	Socio-ecological management	Dissemination		The public disclosure of the project results by any appropriate means (other than resulting from protection or exploiting the results), including scientific publication in any medium. It is the process of promotion and awareness-raising right from the beginning of a project.	https://euromarineassociation.sharepoint.com/:x/r/sites/PREP4BLUE/laouts/15/Doc.aspx?sourcedoc=%7BFA06D110-A86A-4B25-BB8A-0FABED90E1B1%7D&file=PREP4BLUE_Continuous%20Reporting%20Log_v1.1.xlsx.xlsx&action=default&mobileredirect=true	Prep4Blue Continuous Reporting Log

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30	Socio-ecological management	Ecosystem-Based management	EBM	It is an approach developed to work on wicked problems that recognises social-ecological systems and the need to incorporate systems thinking into natural resource management	https://link.springer.com/chapter/10.1007/978-3-030-45843-0_1	Timothy G. O'Higgins, Theodore H. DeWitt, Manuel Lago (2020) Using the Concepts and Tools of Social Ecological Systems and Ecosystem Services to Advance the Practice of Ecosystem-Based Management. Ecosystem-Based Management, Ecosystem Services and Aquatic Biodiversity. ISBN : 978-3-030-45842-3
31	Citizen & Stakeholder engagement	Empower		To place final decision-making in the hands of the public	https://iap2canada.ca/Resources/Documents/0702-Foundations-Spectrum-MW-rev2%20(1).pdf	
32	Citizen engagement	Empowerment		The process through which actors gain the [capacity] to mobilize resources and institutions to achieve a goal. This process of 'gaining capacity' [is unpacked] along three dimensions: (1) access to resources and institutions, (2) strategies to mobilize them and (3) the willingness to do so'	-	Avelino, Flor (2017). Power in Sustainability Transitions: Analysing Power and (Dis)empowerment in Transformative Change Towards Sustainability, <i>Environmental Policy and Governance</i> 27: 505-520
33	Awareness campaigns & Ocean Literacy	end-user		individual(s) who are identified as being in a position where they could feasibly apply a given unit of Knowledge (KO/KER) and by doing so create the desired eventual impact of that knowledge	Prep4Blue PDEC	
34	Socio-ecological management	Energy Efficiency		It means the ratio of output of performance, service, goods or energy to input of energy		
35	Social innovation	European Legislation Identifier	ELI	is a framework to make legislation metadata available online in a standardised format, so that it can be accessed, exchanged and reused across borders	https://zenodo.org/records/10944474	
36	Social innovation	EUropean Research Information Ontology	EURIO	is an ontology developed by CORDIS on the basis of data about research projects funded by the EU's framework programmes for research and innovation following Semantic Web standards	https://zenodo.org/records/10944474	

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37	Modelling	FAIR data		Principle governing data management, which should accomplish: Findability (F), Accessibility (A), Interoperability (I), and Reusability (R).	A-AAGORA project glossary	Wilkinson, M., Dumontier, M., Aalbersberg, I. <i>et al.</i> The FAIR Guiding Principles for scientific data management and stewardship. <i>Sci Data</i> 3, 160018 (2016).
38	Citizen & Stakeholder engagement	Field Trip		A field trip takes interested stakeholders to physical locations.	https://www.fws.gov/stakeholder-engagement/techniques	
39	Citizen & Stakeholder engagement	Focus group		A small discussion group led by a trained moderator to learn about the issues, concerns, and reactions of a particular group of stakeholders to a topic or proposal.	https://www.fws.gov/stakeholder-engagement/techniques	
40	Awareness campaigns & Ocean Literacy	Green skills		Green skills are the competencies and knowledge necessary to support environmental sustainability, reduce ecological impacts, and drive the global shift toward greener practices. Green skills are diverse, ranging from technical to strategic roles, and often intersect with traditional skills as industries increasingly integrate sustainability into conventional job functions. This blending of green and traditional skills is key to preparing the workforce for a rapidly evolving green economy, where adaptability and innovation are essential.	https://www.greenskills.org/definitions.html	
41	Citizen & Stakeholder engagement	Inform		To provide the public with balanced and objective information to assist them in understanding the problem, alternatives and/or solutions	https://iap2canada.ca/Resources/Documents/07-02-Foundations-Spectrum-MW-rev2%20(1).pdf	
42	Citizen & Stakeholder engagement	Involve		To work directly with the public throughout the process to ensure that public concerns and aspirations are consistently understood and considered	https://iap2canada.ca/Resources/Documents/07-02-Foundations-Spectrum-MW-rev2%20(1).pdf	
43	Socio-ecological management	Key Performance Indicator	KPI	The critical (key) quantifiable indicator of progress toward an intended result	A-AAGORA project glossary. www.kpi.org	
44	Citizen & Stakeholder engagement	Key Stakeholder Interviews		Telephone or in-person interviews to obtain in-depth information from key stakeholders.	https://www.fws.gov/stakeholder-engagement/techniques	

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45	Awareness campaigns & Ocean Literacy	Knowledge		The body of facts, principles, theories and practices that is related to a field of work or study. Knowledge is described as theoretical and/or factual, and is the outcome of the assimilation of information through learning.	https://ec.europa.eu/ploteus/sites/eac-eqf/files/en.pdf	European Commission ESCO Handbook, European Skills, Competences, Qualifications and Occupations, © European Union, 2017
46	Awareness campaigns & Ocean Literacy	Knowledge exploitation results	KER	Refers to tangible or intangible outputs of the action, such as data, knowledge and information whatever their form or nature which have been deemed to be of high priority for project transfer actions	https://www.columbusproject.eu/	Definition according to COLUMBUS (Horizon 2020 project: 652690)
47	Awareness campaigns & Ocean Literacy	Knowledge output	KO	Refers to a unit of knowledge that has been generated out of a scientific project. It is not limited to <i>de-novo</i> or pioneering discoveries but may also include new methodologies/processes, adaptations, insights, alternative applications of prior know-how/knowledge	https://www.columbusproject.eu/	Definition according to COLUMBUS (Horizon 2020 project: 652690)
48	Awareness campaigns & Ocean Literacy	Knowledge transfer	KT	Enabling knowledge and ideas to move between knowledge sources to the potential users of the knowledge. It consists of a variety of activities which aim to capture and pass on knowledge, skills and competence from those who generate them to those who can use them	https://www.columbusproject.eu/	Definition according to COLUMBUS (Horizon 2020 project: 652690)
49	Awareness campaigns & Ocean Literacy	Knowledge transfer plan	KTP	Informed stepwise plan for achieving the identified eventual impact of any piece of knowledge, regardless of whether this impact is achievable in the short, medium or long term	https://www.columbusproject.eu/	Definition according to COLUMBUS (Horizon 2020 project: 652690)
50	Macro & micro plastics	Marine biodegradable materials		They are materials that can be broken down by natural processes. They degrade into natural components and do not harm the environment. Examples of biodegradable materials commonly used in the marine environment include plant-based plastics, natural fibres, and biopolymers	https://ts2.space/en/the-role-of-biodegradable-and-eco-friendly-materials-in-marine-and-aquatic-ecosystems/	-
51	Socio-ecological management	Marine Strategy Framework Directive	MSFD	It is a European directive to protect the marine ecosystem and biodiversity upon which our health and marine-related economic and social activities depend.	https://research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/research-area/environment/oceans-and-seas/eu-marine-strategy-framework-directive_en	
52	Macro & micro plastics	Microplastic		They are small pieces of plastics, usually smaller than 5mm. They are persistent, very mobile and hard to remove from nature	https://environment.ec.europa.eu/topics/plastics/microplastics_en	

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53	Awareness campaigns & Ocean Literacy	Mission Ocean Ecosystem	MOE	is a database with the aim of linking the various aspects, actions, partners, and stakeholders to support an efficient exchange of expertise and best practices as well as explore synergies and complementarities within the Mission Restore Our Oceans and Waters	https://wavelinks.eu/	
54	Awareness campaigns & Ocean Literacy	Multiple dimensions of ocean literacy		First introduced in the early 2000s, the concept of ocean literacy has evolved in recent years, not least since its inclusion as a mechanism for change within the United Nations Ocean Decade's goals. Building on early definitions of ocean literacy, there has been increasing recognition of a range of additional dimensions which contribute to an individual or collective sense of 'ocean literacy'. Drawing on existing research and parallel and supporting concepts, e.g., marine citizenship, ocean connectedness, and public perceptions research, this new framework includes ten dimensions of ocean literacy: 1. knowledge 2. communication 3. behaviour 4. awareness 5. attitudes 6. activism 7. emotional connection 8. access and experience 9. adaptive capacity 10. trust and transparency	https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0025326X22011493	E. McKinley, D. Burdon, R.J. Shellock, The evolution of ocean literacy: A new framework for the United Nations Ocean Decade and beyond, Marine Pollution Bulletin, Volume 186, 2023, 114467, ISSN 0025-326X, https://doi.org/10.1016/j.marpolbul.2022.114467 .
55	Awareness campaigns & Ocean Literacy	Natural Capital Skills		Those focused on the concept of the biosphere, the maintenance of ecological balance and the protection of biodiversity.	https://www.greenskills.org/framework.html	
56	Socio-ecological management	Nature-based solutions for ecosystem restoration	NBS	They are understood as actions to protect, conserve, restore, sustainably use and manage natural or modified terrestrial, freshwater, coastal and marine ecosystems, which address social, economic and environmental challenges effectively and adaptively, while simultaneously providing human well-being, ecosystem services and resilience and biodiversity benefits	https://wedocs.unep.org/bitstream/handle/20.500.11822/39864/NATURE-BASED%20SOLUTIONS%20FOR%20SUPPORTING%20SUSTAINABLE%20DEVELOPMENT.%20English.pdf?sequence=1&isAllowed=y	UNEP/EA.5/L9/REV1
57	Citizen engagement	Network		A network is a named group of entities that is concerned with or works on a given topic. Networks persist as specific members come and go, and outside of specific projects, initiatives or pieces of work. Networks connect individuals, organizations, institutions, and projects that share an objective	https://gsnetworks.org/what-is-a-multi-stakeholder-network-for-global-problem-solving/	
58	Social innovation	Nomenclature of Economic Activities	NACE	is the European standard classification of productive economic activities	https://zenodo.org/records/10944474	

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59	Citizen & Stakeholder engagement	Non-governmental organization	NGO	It is an organization that is independent from government control that operates on a not-for-profit level. That includes charities and non-profits.	https://adaoraokoye.medium.com/if-youve-ever-wondered-what-the-difference-between-those-four-terms-are-not-c1e1a32ab834	
60	Awareness campaigns & Ocean Literacy	Ocean health		The exact definition of ocean health varies across locations and stakeholders, but it often consist of a diverse set of management goals related to how people use and value the marine environment.	http://dx.doi.org/10.1890/ES11-00366.1	Samhuri, J. F., S. E. Lester, E. R. Selig, B. S. Halpern, M. J. Fogarty, C. Longo, and K. L. McLeod. 2012. Sea sick? Setting targets to assess ocean health and ecosystem services. <i>Ecosphere</i> 3(5):41
61	Awareness campaigns & Ocean Literacy	Ocean literacy	OL	Understanding of the ocean's influence on human beings and their influence on the ocean.	http://www.coexplorati.on.org/oceanliteracy/documents/OceanLitChart.pdf	National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration (NOAA) (2013). <i>Ocean Literacy: The Essential Principles and Fundamental Concepts of Ocean Sciences for Learners of All Ages. Version 2.</i>
62	Awareness campaigns & Ocean Literacy	Ocean literacy principles		Seven Essential Principles (developed in 44 Fundamental Concepts) identifying the content knowledge that an ocean literate person should know by the end of secondary school. They were developed for the United states, based in a collaborative approach including educators, scientists and Administrations: Principle 1: Earth has one big Ocean with many features. Principle 2: The ocean and life in the ocean shape the features of the Earth. Principle 3: The ocean is a major influence on weather and climate. Principle 4: The ocean made earth habitable. Principle 5: The ocean supports a great diversity of life and ecosystems. Principle 6: The ocean and humans are inextricably interconnected. Principle 7: The ocean is largely unexplored.	http://www.marineboard.eu/publication/review-ocean-literacy-european-maritime-policy https://unesdoc.unesco.org/ark:/48223/pf0000260721	French, V., Chu, N.-C., Santoro, F., Sousa Pinto, I., Borges, D., McDonough, N.(2015). <i>Review of Ocean literacy in European Marine Policy. EU Sea Change Project.</i> F Santoro <i>et al</i> (eds) 2017. <i>Ocean Literacy for all. A toolkit.</i> IOC/UNESCO & UNESCO Venice office, Paris (IOC Manuals and Guides, 80).
63	Awareness campaigns & Ocean Literacy	Ocean sciences education		Refers to education based on the disciplines addressing the global marine environment. The disciplines can be divided into physical oceanography, geological oceanography, chemical oceanography and marine biology.	https://www.bangor.ac.uk/oceansciences/about/what.php.en	

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64	Social innovation	Ontology		is a branch of philosophy and computer science that deals with the study of existence, categorization, and the relationships between different entities or concepts within a specific domain of knowledge. In the context of computer science and information systems, ontologies are used to represent and organize knowledge in a structured and formal manner	https://zenodo.org/records/10944474	
65	Awareness campaigns & Ocean Literacy	Open Discovery Process	ODP	enables engagement, deliberation and path co-creation with variable sets of stakeholders, repurposing the established participatory governance approach of smart specialisation towards sustainability	https://www.researchgate.net/publication/371911954_Regional_Missions_-_Interreg_Europe_Policy_Brief/references	Morisson, Arnault & Pattinson, Marc. (2023). Regional Missions - Interreg Europe Policy Brief
66	Citizen & Stakeholder engagement	Parliament of the sea		unites and represents the maritime community, bringing forward projects and new ideas, innovations, best practices, organize dialogue, debate and mutual understanding. Also carries out national and European lobbying. It has three decision levels: a forum (1573 members), an assembly made up of 4 colleges (212 members) and an executive office (20 members)	https://zenodo.org/records/1094457	
67	Citizen & Stakeholder engagement	Philanthropic organization		Philanthropy is an effort an individual or organization undertakes based on an altruistic desire to improve human welfare, and wealthy individuals sometimes establish private foundations to facilitate their philanthropic efforts.	https://www.investopedia.com/terms/p/philanthropy.asp	
68	Citizen & Stakeholder engagement	Public Engagement		refers to involving members of the public in decisions that impact them. Governments often engage members of the public in decisions about policies, programs and services, but how and why governments engage the public can vary widely	https://www.ncsc.org/consulting-and-research/areas-of-expertise/communications,-civics-and-disinformation/community-engagement/toolkit/why-to-use/the-promise-of-public-engagement/what-is-public-engagement	
69	Citizen & Stakeholder engagement	Public opinion survey or poll		A method of collecting information about the opinions of a group of people with the intention of generalizing the results to a larger population.	https://www.fws.gov/stakeholder-engagement/techniques	

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70	Citizen & Stakeholder engagement	Quadruple helix framework	QH	Refers to the four major sectors of society: industry, government, research, and the public	https://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/documents/downloadPublic?documentIds=080166e5e4d98f00&appId=PPGMS	Carayannis, E.G., Rakhmatullin, R. The Quadruple/Quintuple Innovation Helixes and Smart Specialisation Strategies for Sustainable and Inclusive Growth in Europe and Beyond. J Knowl Econ 5, 212–239 (2014)
71	Citizen & Stakeholder engagement	Research and Technology organizations	RTOs	public or private non-profit organisations that provide a range of research, development and technology services, principally to business and government	https://joint-research-centre.ec.europa.eu/system/files/2015-12/JRC97781.pdf	
72	Social innovation	Semantic network		is a graphical representation of knowledge or information in the form of nodes (representing concepts or entities) and edges (representing relationships or links between these concepts).	https://zenodo.org/records/10944474	
73	Awareness campaigns & Ocean Literacy	Skill		The ability to apply knowledge and use know-how to complete tasks and solve problems. Skills are described as cognitive (involving the use of logical, intuitive and creative thinking) or practical (involving manual dexterity and the use of methods, materials, tools and instruments).	https://ec.europa.eu/ploteus/sites/eac-eqf/files/en.pdf	European Commission ESCO Handbook, European Skills, Competences, Qualifications and Occupations, © European Union, 2017
74	Awareness campaigns & Ocean Literacy	Skill needs		Demand for particular types of skills, competences or qualifications on the labour market (total demand in a country or in a region, economic sector, etc.).	https://www.cedefop.europa.eu/files/4106_en.pdf	CEDEFOP 2011
75	Awareness campaigns & Ocean Literacy	Skill Shortage		Situation where skills supply (type of abilities and number of people available on the labour market) is not sufficient to meet labour market demand. Comments: a skill shortage applies to all levels of qualification; it may result from factors such as - insufficient education and training supply - geographical imbalance in supply - developments impacting the structure of the economy - lack of attractiveness of specific occupations (difficult working or conditions, low remuneration, insufficient social recognition) - lack of attractiveness of specific occupations (difficult work conditions, low remuneration, insufficient social recognition)	https://www.cedefop.europa.eu/files/4106_en.pdf	CEDEFOP 2010

	TOPIC	TERM	ACRONYM	DEFINITION	SOURCE	CITATION
76	Citizen & Stakeholder engagement	Social Labs	SL	They provide research settings for experimenting with possible solutions in the real-life context of particular societal challenges where experts and stakeholders collectively work together to initiate actions focused on addressing these challenges	Hassan, Zaid. 2014. <i>The Social Labs Revolution</i> . San Francisco, CA: Berrett-Koehler Publishers	Marschalek, ilse, Blok, V., Bernstein, M., Braun, R., Cohen, J., Hofer, M., ... Kumar Thapa, R. (2022). The social lab as a method for experimental engagement in participatory research. <i>Journal of Responsible Innovation</i> , 9(3), 419–442. https://doi.org/10.1080/23299460.2022.2119003
77	Citizen & Stakeholder engagement	Social Media		Social media is the collective of online communications channels that enable users to create and share content, and to interact with other users with whom they share a connection.	https://www.fws.gov/stakeholder-engagement/techniques	
78	Socio-ecological management	Social-Ecological Systems	SES	It frames relationships between human and ecological components as part of a complex system with multi-scale feedbacks and dependencies	https://books.google.es/books?hl=en&lr=&id=Y5FnAq9kxgC&oi=fnd&pg=PP1&dq=Berkes,+F.,+J.+Colding,+and+C.+Folke.+2003.+Navigating+Social+Ecological+Systems:+Building+Resilience+for+Complexity+and+Change.+Cambridge+University+Press,+Cambridge&ots=w133civ6Q&sig=TGHhuFOlgr4DNpba4zIndS67fok&redir_esc=y#v=onepage&q&f=false	Berkes, F., J. Colding, and C. Folke. 2003. <i>Navigating Social-Ecological Systems: Building Resilience for Complexity and Change</i> . Cambridge University Press, Cambridge
79	Socio-ecological management	Societal Readiness Level	SRL	Level of knowledge about the stakeholders' interests and concerns as well as to what extent the product/service impacts on society	https://ec.europa.eu/isa2/sites/default/files/technology_readiness_revisited_-_icegov2020.pdf	Bruno, Ilenia, <i>et al.</i> "Technology readiness revisited: a proposal for extending the scope of impact assessment of European public services." <i>Proceedings of the 13th international conference on theory and practice of electronic governance</i> . 2020.
80	Citizen & Stakeholder engagement	Stakeholder		A person such as an employee, customer, or citizen who is involved with an organization, society, etc. and therefore has responsibilities towards it and an interest in its success	https://dictionary.cambridge.org/dictionary/english/stakeholder	

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81	Citizen & Stakeholder engagement	Stakeholder assembly		The stakeholder assembly was inspired by the citizen's assembly model and deliberative democracy, in which a small but diverse and representative sample of people affected by an issue makes inclusive recommendations and conclusions for a larger group. In a stakeholder assembly the discussion is among experts.	Prep4Blue definition	
82	Citizen & Stakeholder engagement	Stakeholder engagement		Stakeholder engagement is a highly relevant activity that builds relationships between parties enabling information exchange. This process allows stakeholder affected by decisions of organisation in question to contribute to the decision-making process	https://grip.eu/how-to-engage-with-qh/	
83	Awareness campaigns & Ocean Literacy	Target user		individuals with a specific mandate or responsibilities relevant to the specific KO/KER being evaluated. Target users should not merely be potential users of knowledge but should be individuals whose application of the knowledge is likely to advance it down the Pathway to Impact	Prep4Blue PDEC	
84	Citizen engagement	Technology Acceptance Model	TAM	The technology acceptance model (TAM) explains the acceptance of information systems by individuals. TAM postulates that the acceptance of technology is predicted by the users' behavioural intention, which is, in turn, determined by the perception of technology usefulness in performing the task and perceived ease of its use	https://open.ncl.ac.uk/theories/1/technology-acceptance-model/	<i>Davis, F. D. (1989), "Perceived usefulness, perceived ease of use, and user acceptance of information technology", MIS Quarterly, 13 (3): 319–340, doi:10.2307/249008</i>
85	Citizen engagement	Technology Adoption Curve	TAC	The technology adoption curve uses the bell curve system to categorize five types of employees and how they react to adopting, accepting, and using new kinds of implemented technology in a business environment.		

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86	Socio-ecological management	Technology readiness level	TRL	Type of measurement system used to assess the maturity level of a particular technology. TRL 1 – basic principles observed; TRL 2 - technology concept formulated; TRL 3 - experimental proof of concept; TRL 4 - technology validated in lab; TRL 5 - technology validated in relevant environment (industrially relevant environment in the case of key enabling technologies); TRL 6 - technology demonstrated in relevant environment (industrially relevant environment in the case of key enabling technologies); TRL 7 - system prototype demonstration in operational environment; TRL 8 - system complete and qualified; TRL 9 - actual system proven in operational environment (competitive manufacturing in the case of key enabling technologies; or in space)	A-AAGORA project glossary.	
87	Awareness campaigns & Ocean Literacy	Transversal knowledge, skills and competences		Knowledge, skills and competences are relevant to a broad range of occupations and sectors	https://ec.europa.eu/ploteus/sites/eac-eqf/files/en.pdf	European Commission ESCO Handbook, European Skills, Competences, Qualifications and Occupations, © European Union, 2017
88	Citizen & Stakeholder engagement	Website		Easily accessible information repositories for broad audiences.	https://www.fws.gov/stakeholder-engagement/techniques	
89	Citizen & Stakeholder engagement	Workshops		A task-oriented meeting where participants are invited to work together on a common problem or issue, often with the goal of producing a product.	https://www.fws.gov/stakeholder-engagement/techniques	
90	Citizen & Stakeholder engagement	World café		A simple, large-group dialogue technique that can be used for engaging stakeholders in face-to-face discussion.	https://www.fws.gov/stakeholder-engagement/techniques	